

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY

ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ

НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ

Научный журнал по научной и инновационной терапии

основано в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

Редакционная коллегия:

*Н.Ш. Ахмедова (зам. главного редактора),
Ш.А. Наимова (ответственный секретарь),
Г.Ж. Жарилкасинова, Н.А. Нуралиев, К.Ж. Болтаев,
Ф.Э. Нурбаев, С.М. Бахрамов, А.Г. Гадаев,
А.Ш. Иноятов, Р.Б. Абдуллаев*

*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

ISSN
2181-418X

2024, № 1

Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

Телефон:

(99865) 223-00-50

Факс

(99866) 223-00-50

Сайт

<https://ivit.uz/>

e-mail

shnaimova5@gmail.com

О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28.05.2022 г.

Подписано в печать 20.11.2023.

Формат 60×84 1/8

Усл. П.л. 41,39

Заказ 104

Тираж 50 экз.

Отпечатано в типографии Шарк

140151, г. Бухары,

ул. Амира Темура, 18

Редакционный совет:

Anand Ahuja	(Индия)
Nordin Simbak	(Малайзия)
Tetsuo Sasano	(Япония)
Ali O'zdemir	(Туркия)
Есаян А.М.	(Россия)
Арипова Т.У.	(Узбекистан)
Ахмедов Р.М.	(Узбекистан)
Амонов М.К.	(Узбекистан)
Бадритдинова М.Н.	(Узбекистан)
Бобоев К.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Давлатов С.С.	(Узбекистан)
Дустова Н.К.	(Узбекистан)
Курманова Г.М.	(Казахстан)
Қаюмов А.А.	(Узбекистан)
Мавлянов З.И.	(Узбекистан)
Набиева Д.А.	(Узбекистан)
Неъматов Ж.М.	(Узбекистан)
Рахматова Д.И.	(Узбекистан)
Саноева М.Ж.	(Узбекистан)
Сулаймонова Г.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Тўракулов Р.И.	(Узбекистан)
Шодидулова Г.З.	(Узбекистан)
Эгамова С.Қ.	(Узбекистан)
Юлдашева Д.Х.	(Узбекистан)
Убайдуллаева З.И.	(Узбекистан)

**IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF A DEPARTMENTAL MEDICAL
INSTITUTION IN A HIGHLY COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT
GROMOV PETR VLADIMIROVICH**

PhD, MBA, anesthesiologist-intensive care specialist of the highest category, director
of the private healthcare institution «Clinical Hospital «RZD-Medicine» of St.
Petersburg», gromovpv@rwmed.ru

Abstract. The article considers some approaches in corporate management, related to the processes of transformation and improvement of clinical medical care in order to increase the competitive stability of the departmental organization in the highly competitive megapolis market in St. Petersburg, Russian Federation.

Keywords: management of a medical organization, industrial medicine, corporate values, customer service, competitiveness.

Today's medical service management involves not only managing its structural elements and business processes, but also positioning the institution for competitiveness. It should be noted that our strategic goal is the continuous development of the institution and the strengthening of competencies, focused on the continuous improvement of quantitative and qualitative indicators of the provision of medical services to patients.

The Russian Railways-Medicine Clinical Hospital in St. Petersburg is component of the unified Russian Railways-Medicine healthcare network, the largest network of private healthcare institutions in Russia and is the largest multidisciplinary medical and preventive institution in the Northwestern Federal District of the Russian Federation with a 110-year history (founded in 1914). The main function of the Clinical Hospital is to support the activities of the holding company of the Russian Railways and to maintain the professional health and longevity of its employees for the safety of train traffic. The Clinical Hospital was founded in 1914 and during the 110 years of its existence the hospital developed unique methods of industrial medicine, including those related to professional risks.

From the very beginning the clinical hospital functioned as a hospital for workers and employees of the railway, but today, in accordance with the changed reality, it has turned into a medical institution whose services are available to all residents of Saint Petersburg and the Leningrad region, other regions of the Russian Federation, as well as near and far abroad. There are closed cycles of diagnosis and treatment of almost all organs and systems. The diagnostic complex of the Clinical Hospital is open 24/7 for both specialized and emergency medical care (CT, MRI, ultrasound, endoscopy, densitometry, intravascular ultrasound, angiography). The Clinical Hospital is well equipped with an advanced medical equipment, obtained state licenses for the right to provide high-tech medical care in almost every field of medicine, including general surgery, ophthalmology, gynecology, Otorhinolaryngology, maxillofacial surgery, traumatology and orthopedics, urology, Coloproctology, neurosurgery, oncology, cardiovascular surgery, endocrinology.

The hospital operates in the highly competitive medical services market of the megapolis. The number of medical institutions in this sector continues to increase. At present, according to BusinesStat consulting company data, commercial medical institutions predominate among all health care organizations in Saint Petersburg. On average, in 2018-2022, private organizations accounted for 78.7% of the city's medical institutions [p.15, 9]. It is essential that we increase patient loyalty and maintain the competitiveness of the institution in these circumstances.

It is well known that the significance of social services for customers is vital to any business, particularly when it comes to medical services. The value is having the utmost importance not only in the context of obtaining final economic benefits, but most importantly – in the context of relationships with end users, patients. That is why the orientation to the customer needs is a major trend that cannot be ignored [p.19, 3]. A study conducted by the RosExpert consulting company on the profile of executives who currently manage Russian businesses and those who will manage them in 2026. One of the strategic competencies included in the "Success Profile 2026" rating compiled by RosExpert company is customer orientation and the ability

to see customer needs as a key priority, find optimal solutions to meet their current and future needs, build productive long-term relationships with customers and create systems that can shape and sustain these relationships in the very near future [10].

To better understand the perception of the value of medical services by customers, we conducted in-depth interviews and questionnaires on a *representative group* of patients – employees of locomotive crews of the Oktyabrsky Polygon railway line, who received medical services both stationary in the hospital and in the outpatient polyclinic of the institution. As a result of our research, some values and guidelines were revealed, which we consider correct to use as fundamental factors in the formation of the further functioning of the institution and the analysis of mechanisms for bringing value to consumers of medical services, and, as a result, for the transformation of the existing business model. The obtained results of conduct research are presented below in table 1.

Table 1.

Values revealed	Percentage of respondents (<i>hospital patients</i>)	Percentage of respondents (<i>polyclinic patients</i>)	Average percentage
money savings	15	21	18
territorial accessibility	9	27	18
quality of medical services and personnel professional qualifications	39	31	35
service component including service speed and customer focus	27	16	21,5
other responses	10	5	7,5

According to the obtained results, among the identified values, the most important and often mentioned ones were “service” queries. The institution has developed standards of professional ethics, and regularly works with the staff to strengthen customer orientation, but it is obvious that these measures were not enough. More thorough and detailed organizational changes were necessary to improve the existing

mechanisms of customer interaction and convey the company's values. Our company's corporate values, which include health, professionalism, quality, responsibility, and patient orientation, echo the identified consumer values of quality of treatment and patient orientation. We also conducted an analysis of the patient's path, as a result of which we identified the need to improve existing business processes in the direction of strengthening the client-centricity of the medical organization. As a result, we came into conclusion that it is necessary to change the structure of the organization for better interaction with consumers, to change the quality of internal communications between structural divisions, and after building a clear and well-established medical service component. A decision was made to transform the clinic's management system in terms of mechanisms and ways to bring the company's values to the consumer, namely, the creation of a fundamentally new organizational structure within the institution – the Customer Service Center (CSC). As we believe the proposed approach will minimize some of the gaps and bottlenecks that unfortunately still exist in today's patient care model and the objectives of increasing patient satisfaction and market competitiveness of the clinic will be achieved. By combining and centralizing the management of three big registries previously located in different structural divisions of the clinic, the CSC is created as an independent structural unit of the clinic. It should be noted that, following the current trend of business processes digitalization in the modern market of services, we have improved the organizational and technical support of the CSC and it began to carry out its activities in cooperation with the structural divisions of the institution in order to increase the speed of patient care.

The break-even point was established just after 4 months of CSC project being launched, according to calculations. The payback period of the project was 5 months. The proposed project and the investments invested in it both paid off during this period, as shown in the graph presented in Fig.1.

Fig.1. The break-even point of the CSC project

During the first year of operation of the CSC, the indicators of patient satisfaction with the service component of the clinic have improved significantly. During the first year of the CSC project's launch, the percentage of satisfied clinic patients increased from 22% to 37% among respondents. The introduction of CSC optimizes business processes in the provision of medical services and increases patient loyalty, which, in turn, allows you to increase not only the financial performance of the institution, but also the number of people served, increasing the occupied share in the medical services market, increasing its client-centricity, and as a result, and competitiveness.

We note the importance and significance of the reforms carried out not only for the development of the institution and further improvement of the quality of services provided, but also for the development and strengthening of the quality of industrial medicine, which does not stand still, but develops and keeps pace with the times. Summing up, we may conclude that the transformation and improvement of the management system of a departmental medical institution allows us to set some new

ambitious goals and systematically achieve them, maintaining a high standards of customer service and quality of medical care, primarily for railway employees, performing their main functions – ensuring train safety and preserving the professional longevity of railway employees.

References

1. Aivazov A. L., Eremicheva A. N., Nemesh O. I. Strategy in building business models // Scientific and methodological electronic journal "Concept». – 2016. – № S16. – 0,3 п. л. – URL: <http://e-koncept.ru/2016/76181.htm>.
2. Denisov I. V., Velinov E., Viter K. A., Busalova A.D. Business model: the history of the concept development in foreign and domestic scientific publications // Leadership and management. – 2019. – Volume 6. – No. 4. – pp. 385-396. doi: 10.18334/lim.6.4.41241
3. Johnson M., Kagerman H., Christensen K. The secret to a thriving business is understanding the need for fundamental change. Re-invention of the business model // "Innovation Management" 2011 No.2
4. Osterwalder A. Invincible company: How to continuously update the business model of your organization, inspired by the experience of the best. - M.: Alpina Publisher, 2021.
5. Osterwalder A. Building business models. — M.: Alpina Publisher Business, 2017.
6. Ponomareva E. "Time to do business". - M.: MYTH, 2023.
7. Jang Kim and Rene Mauborn. The strategy of the Blue Ocean. – M.: printing house Novosti, 2005.
8. Chinaryan R.A. The client component of the key concepts of universal business models (part 3) // "Clienting and client portfolio management" 2014 No.4
9. *BusinesStat* "Analysis of the medical services market in St. Petersburg in 2018-2022, forecast for 2023-2027. under the conditions of sanctions".
10. "Competencies of the future. Who will run the business in Russia in 2026." t.me/rosexpert_consulting